

Sensor Setup for Force and Finger Position and Tilt Measurements for Pianists

T. Grosshauser

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
ETH Zürich
Collegium Helveticum
Grosshauser@ife.ee.ethz.ch

B. Tessorf, G. Tröster

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
ETH Zürich
tessorf@ife.ee.ethz.ch
troester@ife.ee.ethz.ch

H. Hildebrandt, V. Candia

Collegium Helveticum
ZHdK Zürich
horst.hildebrandt@zhdk.ch
candia@collegium.ethz.ch

ABSTRACT

Finger force, acceleration and position are fundamental in playing music instruments. Measuring these parameters is a technical challenge and precise position and acceleration measurement of single fingers is particularly demanding. We present a sensor setup for multi modal measurements of force, position and acceleration in piano playing. We capture outputs from the upper extremity contributing to the total force output seen at the fingers. To precisely characterize fingers' positions and acceleration we use wearable sensors. A 6-axes (3-force and 3-torque axes) force sensor precisely captures contributions from hand, wrist and arm. A finger's acceleration sensor and a MIDI grand piano complete the measuring setup. The acceleration and position sensor is fixed to the dorsal aspect of the last finger phalanx. The 6-axes sensor is adjustable to fit individual hand positions and constitutes a basis setup that can be easily expanded to account for diverse measurement needs. An existing software tool was adapted to visualize the sensor data and to synchronize it to the MIDI out. With this basis setup we seek to estimate the isolated force output of finger effectors and to show coherences of finger position, force and attack. To proof the setup, a few pilot measurements were carried out.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many parameters are measured regarding motion and gesture in musical instrument playing. Regarding finger force measurements, several attempts have been made to gather information on this parameter to objectively characterize typical force profiles while playing the piano. For example, Parlitz (see Parlitz et al. in [1]) used thin foils placed below the piano keys and was able to show force profiles of key depressions of professional musicians compared to amateurs. Nevertheless, such approaches do not consider force components arising from arm segments other than the fingers. Another approach used a tapping tablet with miniature strain-gauge force transducers to monitor the striking forces generated by the tips of the fingers during tapping (see Aoki et al. in [2]). Even if the approach considered a rest plate for the wrist, and in so doing neutralized several

hand and arm segments from the tracked force, such an approach cannot account for the mechanics of key instruments like the piano. While older schools favored isolated finger work with the only inclusion of arm movements for the horizontal displacement of the hand while playing the cembalo, the nineteenth piano pedagogic favored the addition of the contribution of arm segments in the production of playing force (see Hadjakos in [3]). Diverse research lines have clearly shown that in playing the piano, several arm segments other than the fingers are usually activated and coordinated during attempts to depress piano keys and that this is different for professionals in comparison to amateurs (see for example Furuya et al. in [4]). Moreover, the inclusion of different arm segments has been shown to affect sound production in piano playing, see Furuya et al. in [5]. In addition, Hadjakos (see Hadjakos in [3]) has shown by means of inertial sensing secondary movements resulting from manual excursions during piano playing. Regarding precise measurements of position and acceleration of single fingers while playing a musical instrument the task has revealed to be particularly demanding. In case of optical approaches, the simultaneous single finger movements temporarily occlude each other. In case of hand gloves approaches, the natural finger movements are not possible at all and basically change movement dynamics of finger use resulting in more or less unrealistic estimates. An alternative solution is to use a small wearable sensor board to detect the tilt and acceleration of each finger. In so doing, a realistic and relatively unobtrusive measurement can be achieved.

A calibration routine for adjustment of the sensor and to avoid drift will be integrated in the next, smaller version of the sensor setup. Integrating the information from above, in this paper, we present a basic sensor setup for multi modal measurements of hand and fingers in piano playing. The aim is to accurately capture force outputs arising from hand and arm segments contributing to the total force output measurable at the fingers to be able to better estimate the isolate force contribution of finger effectors. The latter is of importance, as it can be assumed that the fingers are particularly vulnerable to display fatigue and to suffer from musicians' related illnesses, which probably result from exaggerated hand use (see for example Candia et al. in [6] and [7]). Today, several technologies for motion and gestures' detection during instrumental musical playing exist. Early approaches by Turner [8] and Moog et al. [9] show mechanical sensing technology integrated into a Bösendor-

fer 290 SE Recording piano and a 2 dimensional finger position recognition system, the so called “Moog Multiply-Touch-Sensitive” keyboard. McPherson et al. [10] shows capacitive finger location sensing. Several projects about physical modeling of the string with or without the relation to the key attack exist. Close to our approach, is the experiment of Goebel et al. in [11]. They measure the accuracy of the reproduction of computer controlled pianos to examine the reliability of a Yamaha Disklavier grand piano and a B^ösendorfer SE290 for performance research. Minetti et al. in [12] uses a similar sensor equipped commercially available MIDI grand piano to quantitatively assess the technical side of pianist’s performance. With this setup, we wanted to build a modular and extendable platform for multi modal measurements. In the first configuration, we combine a standard Yamaha MIDI grand piano with several new sensors. On the one hand, a 3-axes torque and 3-axes force sensor to measure the force outputs seen at players’ hand. On the other hand, a small wearable sensor board to detect the position and acceleration of each finger. The setup allows precise measurements of the above mentioned parameters and an additional MIDI note representation simplifies data annotation and analysis. The overall goal is to support musicians and music teachers in daily exercising, particularly during their technical training. Here, different sensors are used to show hidden, but meaningful force and movement parameters of music making. One important aim is to test and provide systems for data acquisition in fields not explored so far and to develop measurement methods for playing parameters, which are often discussed among musicians, but which are difficult – if not impossible – to see with the naked eye.

2. STATE OF THE ART AND TECHNICAL OVERVIEW

Numerous and recent research projects, using various methodologies, integrated sensing technologies to musical instruments. Early approaches [9] show mechanical sensing technology integrated into a Bösendorfer 290 SE Recording piano and a 2 dimensional finger position recognition system, the so called “Moog Multiply-Touch-Sensitive Keyboard”. Seminal work was also performed by researchers from Bevilacqua et al. in [13] at IRCAM¹, further at MIT Media Lab² and NOTAM³. These institutions stated several technology driven projects on motion and gesture recognition in the music field. Several previous investigations are close to our approach like those by Goebel et al. in [11]. Here, the accuracy of the reproduction of computer controlled pianos were investigated to examine the reliability of a Yamaha Disklavier grand piano and a Bösendorfer SE290 for performance research. In addition, Minetti [12] used a similar sensor-equipped commercially available MIDI grand piano to quantitatively assess technical aspects of pianists’ performance. In the domain of piano teaching, Hadjakos et al. [14] used inertial sensor measurements in various piano playing and gesture recog-

¹ Institut de Recherche et Coordination Acoustique/Musique

² Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Media Lab

³ Norwegian Center for Technology in Music and Art

nition studies. In this line of research, Goebel et al. [15] describes a technical setup that also uses inertial sensors together with a calibrated microphone to detect general hammer and key movements without measuring finger and hand gestures. Goebel et al. aligned and analyzed the data of different keystrokes, keys, key velocity and the middle panel hammer velocity in relation to the amplitude of the sound signal of different pianos of several manufacturers. High-speed-camera keystroke recognition was explored by Möller [16].

For the operation of the last mentioned video and marker based technologies, many visual markers have to be fixed on the instrument and the human body and several high-speed infrared cameras have to be installed around the observed object. In our approach, we focused on the position of the finger and the force and torque of the hand and the arm during playing in combination with a MIDI grand piano. There are two possibilities of keystroke and fingertip position recognition. The first is to attach the sensors onto the keys (high cost), the second is to fix one sensor on each fingertip (low cost). The low cost system described here is fast enough to detect the maximum forces and the gradient of each finger in different playing modes, like thrills or fast scales. Common key stroke recognition works with two measurement points and the delay between them with every stroke. Van den Berghe describes such a system in [17] and mentions the unsatisfying possibilities to create differentiated key strokes on electric pianos. Also our MIDI grand piano works with simple key sensors for attack recognition. The mechanic itself feels very natural and in combination with other sensors described in the next section it rounds up our present setup, providing an useful overview of the most important playing parameters.

3. TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The measurement setup consists of 3 main components, a MIDI grand piano, a body worn sensor board and a 6-axes force sensor. The wearable sensor board is fixed directly on the fingers (see Fig. 1). The 6-axes force sensor is fixed in front of the keyboard and is adaptable to the pianists’ hand position (see Fig. 2). All sensor data are recorded with a notebook running ToolBox.

3.1 Wearable Sensors

3.1.1 Fixation and Practical Usage

The sensor board is fixed with 3M 4004 Scotch Mount double sided PU-tape. The data are transferred to a laptop computer with ANT+ communication protocol⁴. Due to lower weight, cables are used for power supply, instead of a battery. Batteries usually are small button cells providing 3V output. The sensor board will be replaced by a smaller one, soon, dimensions around 10 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm.

3.1.2 Technical Description

The wearable sensor board, is a wireless sensor board with ANT+ communication protocol. The dimensions are

⁴ <http://www.thisisant.com>

Figure 1. Miniature sensor board with 3-axis acceleration sensors and ANT based wireless data transmission. The cables shown in the picture are for power supply. The batteries of the board are removed to reduce weight. The hand is placed on the 6-axes sensor (see Sec. 3.2).

20 mm×10 mm×3 mm and the weight is 1 g (without battery). The wearable sensor board is equipped with a tri-axial Bosch SMB380 (10-bit) digital MEMS accelerometer. Acceleration can be measured with a bandwidth of up to 1.5 kHz in ranges of $\pm 2\text{ g}/\pm 4\text{ g}/\pm 8\text{ g}$ corresponding to a resolution of 4.0 mg/7.8 mg/15.6 mg. Power supply voltage ranges from 2.4 V to 3.6 V. When active, the microprocessor periodically reads sensor values and sends messages to the radio transceiver according to the ANT message protocol (further technical description see at Kusserow et al. [18]).

3.2 3-Axis Force and 3-Axes Torque Sensor

The multi-axis sensor K6D is suitable for the force and torque measurements in three mutually perpendicular axes. It is adjustable with a self-developed mount attached to the grand piano. This mount (see Fig. 2) is displaceable in all three axes and adaptable to the individual hand position of the player. The mount can be used in fixed position or movable in at least one of each dimension.

3.2.1 K6D Specification

The low weight and form factor of the multi-axis sensor (only 160 g) makes it ideal for our purposes. The maximum specified measuring range of the 6-axes force-torque sensor is: F_x : 500 N, F_y : 500 N, F_z : 2 kN, M_x : 20 Nm, M_y : 20 Nm, M_z : 20 Nm. The dimensions are: diameter 60 mm×40 mm connected with the peripheral equipment via a 5 m long 16-pin cable.

3.2.2 Measurement Amplifier “GSV-1A8US”

We use the GSV-1A8USB 8-channel strain gauge amplifier, suitable for full, half and quarter bridges. The 8×DMS input connectors are connected with the K6D multi-axis sensor. The cutoff frequency is at 250 Hz, input sen-

Figure 2. Adjustable 6-axes force and torque sensor attached to the front of the Yamaha MIDI grand piano. The hand rest and the position of the sensor can be adjusted individually, to the size of the hand, by means of a custom made cast, and the hand in relation to the grand piano keyboard.

sitivity is around 2 mV/V, meaning the measurement precision is below 0.02 N. A zero enforcement button allows easy zero point adjustment. Internally, a National Instruments OEM Card with 200 kHz, 16bit and an over all sampling rate of 250 kHz is used. A USB port and a 37-pole Sub-D connector are integrated.

sitivity is around 2 mV/V, meaning the measurement precision is below 0.02 N. A zero enforcement button allows easy zero point adjustment. Internally, a National Instruments OEM Card with 200 kHz, 16bit and an over all sampling rate of 250 kHz is used. A USB port and a 37-pole Sub-D connector are integrated.

3.2.3 Software GSVMulti and Adjustment Possibilities

The GSVMulti software allows data recording of the K6D 6-axis force-torque sensor and several adjustments. The scanning frequency of the standard software can be adjusted from 1–100 Hz and the amount of channels can be selected. Also the force vector can be adjusted. In our measurement, the balance point of the hand is around 1.5 cm over the center of the sensor. The sensor can be adjusted in all 3 dimensions to obtain the force and torque applied in the balance point. That means, even positions in the front/back or beside the sensor are adjustable and the force and torque applied to the balance point of the hand can be calculated by means of an integrated software tool. Further, a calibration matrix with automatic error correction for the K6D is delivered from the manufacturer to obtain precise values. 36 calibration factors are used to calculate the scale of the sensor signals to each of the 3 axes: Force: F_x , F_y , F_z , and Torque: $a_u x$, $a_u y$, $a_u z$.

3.2.4 Individually Adapted Hand Rest

In order to accomplish individual hand anatomical needs, a changeable hand-fixation and hand-placing holder was constructed. The holder can be easily attached on the top of the adjustable 6-axes force and torque sensor by means of screws (see Fig. 2). The holder can be easily made of thermoplastic material by immersing a rectangular strip with

Figure 3. Illustration of the three axes of torque and force. The hand is positioned above the sensor. The balance point of the hand above the sensor can be adjusted to obtain the precise force and torque values.

an approximate wide of 2 cm and individual length briefly into hot water (ca. 70 ° C, but note that temperatures may vary depending on the thermoplastic material being used). Thereafter, the material can be perfectly tailored to fit individual anatomy without any danger. By waiting a few seconds, a rigid cast preserving individual hand anatomy is obtained (see Fig. 4). The material is very often used for medical devices and has excellent properties for our particular task including adequate stiffness (particularly important to avoid unwanted material deformations during acceleration and force measurements, robustness (important to avoid sudden device deterioration due large force outputs and sudden arm and hand accelerations, and to guarantee the same positioning of a particular hand during repeated measurements) and lightness. Total construction and montage time is ca. 15 min. Although the fixation of the hand does not allow free movement of the hand, it fulfills the requirements of repeated experiments, where the same hand position is required for each execution.

3.3 Yamaha MIDI Grand Piano

We used a Yamaha Silent Grand Piano C3⁵. Key, hammer and pedal sensors register every motion, including key release velocity. Several sensors detect the most important parameters, all of them measurable within the grand piano. The measured parameters are as follows: Sensor/Driver: Hammer Sensors (Noncontact 2-point optical fiber sensor); Key Sensors (Noncontact continuous detection optical sensor); Pedal Sensors: Damper pedal (continuous detection sensor, Sostenuto pedal: ON/OFF detection sensor, Shift pedal: ON/OFF detection sensor. The Yamaha MIDI grand piano further provides a silent mode. By these means it is possible to silence the piano and still preserve the real feedback of instrumental mechanics. The standard connectors are: MIDI (In/Out); AUX IN (In); AUX OUT (Out).

⁵ http://usa.yamaha.com/products/musical-instruments/keyboards/silentpianos/grand_pianos/c3sg/?mode=model

Figure 4. Depicted is the right hand placed in a dummy resembling the adjustable 6-axes force and torque sensor with the cast. Note that by using a ca. 2 cm wide cast it is possible to obtain both good anatomical placement and fixation as well as free movements for all fingers.

3.4 USB Interface “MIDI Prodipe 1i1o”

We used a MIDI USB Prodipe 1i1o⁶ 1 in and 1 out interface. MIDI data transmission further includes 16 MIDI input channels and 16 MIDI output channels. We use it for data transmission to the laptop, gathering all sensor data.

3.5 Recording and Synchronization Framework “CRN ToolBox”

The “Context Recognition Network” (CRN) Toolbox⁷ (see further information in Bannach et al. [19]) allows to quickly build distributed, multi-modal context recognition systems by simply plugging together reusable, parameterizable components. The CRN Toolbox was designed as a runtime system to control the data of parameterizable sensor interfaces flow and handles synchronization. It further offers a development environment offering a set of parameterizable filter, feature and classifier components. The CRN Toolbox is implemented in a modular manner which allowed us to easily adapt it to our specific sensor configuration. We use it to:

1. record all sensor data centrally on a notebook
2. synchronize data based on time stamps
3. annotate data in real-time using the notebook’s keyboard
4. streaming sensor data via a TCP/IP-based interface component for real-time visualization.

3.5.1 Mini DV Camcorder Extension

A small DV Camcorder PMDV80, or any other cam can be fixed additionally beside the piano keyboard. In several experiments we used the above mentioned camera

⁶ <http://www.prodipe.com/en/products/interfaces/item/59-interface-1in/1out>

⁷ http://wiki.esl.fim.uni-passau.de/index.php/CRN_Toolbox

Figure 5. Data flow from the multi modal user input to the final data storage and visualization with the CRN tool box software. To fit individual needs and problem statements, more sensors can be attached to the platform.

for unobtrusive recordings. Video resolution is 720×480 , 1.3 mega-pixel, frame rate is 30 fps and the size is $52 \times 18 \times 8$ mm. Although not necessary for the measurements, its use is of great support in aligning and analyzing the recorded sensor data. As additional gain, the CV camcorder provides a particularly interesting view to the fingers. Relevant points of interest within this specific scenario are the position and movement of the finger on the keyboard.

4. MEASUREMENTS AND PROOF OF CONCEPT

4.1 Multi Modal Sensing and Data Flow

Fig. 5 shows the data flow from the sensors to the final visualization and data storage. The multiple sensor outputs and the MIDI out of the grand piano are merged and recorded with the CRN tool box and the GSVMulti software and synchronized automatically. The unstable delay of the MIDI signal of 4 or more ms is not yet considered. The synchronized data can be visualized with tools like MatLab. This allows the visual analysis of the recorded data in relation to the MIDI notes of the grand piano. The platform can be adapted to individual needs by adding more sensors. Also the visualization and feedback generation in general can involve different modalities and types. This could be implemented into existing software or based on former real-time feedback studies as for example Grosshauser et al. in [20] and [21]. In the following Fig. 6 only one note was played, represented with the green line.

Figure 7. The acceleration measurements and the MIDI out of the grand piano are shown. The red line shows the tilt of the finger and the small spikes the acceleration of the finger tip. The latter clearly indicates the attack (red dot at vertical line B, green dot “note on”) and release (green dot “note off” at vertical line B of the finger on the key).

4.2 Example of a Data Recording

Fig. 6 shows the measured data of the piano player’s second finger, repeating one note 26 times. The plot shows that the sensor system and data fusion and synchronization works properly. Data is shown as follows: Torque and force of the hand correspond clearly; the increase of force in the z-axis (down force, caused by the hand) occurs simultaneously with the torque (between 127 and 143 s). Although only one note is played and the hand seems to stay calm, a little torque can be captured. The acceleration measurements, see Fig. 7, show the tilt of the finger (red line) and the acceleration of each attack (red dot at vertical line B, green dot “note on”) and release (green dot “note off” at vertical line B).

The tilt of the finger corresponds with the position of the contact point of the finger with the piano keys. Therefore, conclusions on the tilt of the finger and the position on a key can be drawn. Furthermore, the amount of force in the finger only, and the force from the elbow or upper arm can be also estimated. In addition, changes of the finger/arm force distribution indicating if the key attack is low or high can be computed. To sum up, the combination of all these sensor data streams allows meaningful conclusions and precise measurement and visualization of several playing parameters.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The described basic measurement’s setup represents a further step to gathering objective data regarding finger, hand and arm force as well as finger position and acceleration used in playing the piano. Importantly, the work represents a new step towards novel measurement setups to quantify

Figure 6. Recorded data within one recording session is plotted. The first row shows the x-, y- and z-axis of the applied hand force, the second row shows the three axis of hand torques, the third row the 3 axis of the 2nd finger’s acceleration (the small spikes) and tilt (slow change of the e.g. between 130 and 135 sec.) and the fourth row shows the MIDI notes (note on/off, the higher dots, MIDI 2) and different attacks (the lower dots, MIDI 3).

usually hidden parameters pivotal to music making, which are impossible to uncover objectively by means of mere observation. With the presented measurement setup and sensors it is possible to measure parameters like force and torque captured at the hand segment in a horizontal position, parallel to the key arrangement. Thus, force and acceleration of arm rotations, frontal displacements and their combinations can be accurately measured at the hand-sensor interface. In addition, different finger attacks that imply different angular configurations of the fingers in relation to the depressed keys become unobtrusively measurable. The next steps will also consider the inclusion of smaller inertial sensors depicting the parallel action of all hand fingers to capture differences in work profiles of fingers during instrumental maneuvers, as well as the development of a low-friction 6-axes sensor montage to allow measurements of more complex piano playing tasks involving horizontal arm displacements. Ultimately, all this information will contribute to the development of new methods of instrumental training.

Acknowledgments

This project has been supported partly by the Swiss National Science Foundation.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] D. Parlitz, T. Peschel, and E. Altenmüller, “Assessment of dynamic finger forces in pianists: Effects of training and expertise,” *Journal of Biomechanics*, vol. 31, no. 11, pp. 1063 – 1067, 1998.
- [2] T. Aoki, S. Furuya, and H. Kinoshita, “Finger-tapping ability in male and female pianists and nonmusician controls,” *Motor Control*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 23–39, Jan 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hubmed.org/display.cgi?uids=15784948>
- [3] A. Hadjakos, “Sensor-based feedback for piano pedagogy, phd thesis,” Ph.D. dissertation, Technischen Universität Darmstadt, 2011.
- [4] S. Furuya, T. Goda, H. Katayose, H. Miwa, and N. Nagata, “Distinct inter-joint coordination during fast alternate keystrokes in pianists with superior skill,” *Front Hum Neurosci*, vol. 5, pp. 50–50, 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hubmed.org/display.cgi?uids=21660290>
- [5] S. Furuya, E. Altenmüller, H. Katayose, and H. Kinoshita, “Control of multi-joint arm movements for the manipulation of touch in keystroke by expert pianists,” *BMC Neurosci*, vol. 11, pp. 82–82, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hubmed.org/display.cgi?uids=20630085>
- [6] V. Candia, C. Wienbruch, T. Elbert, B. Rockstroh, and W. Ray, “Effective behavioral treatment of focal hand dystonia in musicians alters somatosensory cortical organization,” *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, vol. 100, no. 13, pp. 7942–7946, Jun 2003. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hubmed.org/display.cgi?uids=12771383>
- [7] V. Candia, J. Rosset-Llobet, T. Elbert, and A. Pascual-Leone, “Changing the brain through therapy for

- musicians' hand dystonia," *Ann N Y Acad Sci*, vol. 1060, pp. 335–342, Dec 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hubmed.org/display.cgi?uids=16597783>
- [8] E. O. Turner, "Touch and tone-quality: The pianist's illusion," in *The Musical Times*, Vol. 80, No. 1153 (Mar. 1939), pp. 173-176.
- [9] R. Moog and T. Rhea, "Evolution of the keyboard interface: The boesendorfer 290 se recording piano and the moog multiply-touch-sensitive keyboards," in *Computer Music Journal Vol. 14 No. 2, New Performance Interfaces 2*, 1990.
- [10] A. McPherson and Y. Kim, "Design and applications of a multi-touch musical keyboard," in *SMC 2011, 8th Sound and Music Computing Conference*.
- [11] W. Goebel and R. Bresin, "Measurement and reproduction accuracy of computer-controlled grand pianos," in *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America / Volume 114 / Issue 4 / MUSIC AND MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS*, 2003.
- [12] A. Minetti, L. Ardigo, and T. McKee, "Keystroke dynamics and timing: Accuracy, precision and difference between hands in pianist's performance," in *Journal of Biomechanics*, 2007.
- [13] F. Bevilacqua, N. Rasamimanana, E. Fléty, S. Lemouton, and F. Baschet, "The augmented violin project: research, composition and performance report," in *NIME '06: Proceedings of the 2006 conference on New interfaces for musical expression*. Paris, France, France: IRCAM — Centre Pompidou, 2006, pp. 402–406.
- [14] A. Hadjakos, E. Aitenbichler, and M. Muehlhaeuser, "Potential use of inertial measurement sensors for piano teaching systems: Motion analysis of piano playing patterns," 4th i-Maestro Workshop on Technology-Enhanced Music Education, 2008.
- [15] W. Goebel, R. Bresin, and A. Galembo, "Touch and temporal behavior of grand piano actions," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 118(2), p. 11541165, 2005.
- [16] R. Moeller and Wentorf, "High-speed-camera recording of pulp deformation while playing piano or clavichord," in *Musikphysiologie und Musikmedizin*, no. 11. Jg., Nr. 4, 2004.
- [17] G. Van den Berghe, B. De Moor, and W. Minten, "Modeling a grand piano key action," in *Computer Music Journal*, Vol. 19, No. 2. The MIT Press, 1995.
- [18] M. Kusserow, O. Amft, and G. Troester, "Bodyant: Miniature wireless sensors for naturalistic monitoring of daily activity," in *BodyNets 09*, Los Angeles, CA, USA.
- [19] D. Bannach, K. Kunze, and P. Lukowicz, "Distributed modular toolbox for multi-modal context recognition," in *Proc. Architecture of Computing Systems. ARCS 2006*. Springer LNCS 2006, Vol. 3894/2006, 99-113.
- [20] T. Grosshauser and T. Hermann, "Augmented haptics - an interactive feedback system for musicians," in *Haptic and Audio Interaction Design, 4th International Conference, HAID 2009, Dresden, Germany, September 10-11, 2009, Proceedings*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, M. E. Altinsoy, U. Jekosch, and S. A. Brewster, Eds., vol. 5763. Springer, September 2009, pp. 100–108.
- [21] ———, "Flexible sensor setups and embedded pattern recognition for motion and gesture analysis and learning," in *International Symposium on Music Acoustics, ViennaTalk2010*, 2010.